

THE IMPORTANCE OF PHRASEOLOGY IN TEACHING A LANGUAGE

*N. Iskandarova*¹

Abstract:

This article devoted to analyze the importance of phraseology in teaching a language. Moreover, information about classification of phraseological units in English were noted.

Key words: phraseological unit, lingual aspects, corpus linguists, verbum meaning, words-components, phraseological synonyms

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Introduction

One area that is a source of some confusion in second language acquisition is the field of phraseology that is defined as the study of word combinations and a phraseological unit is defined as being made up of at least two words. It is rather difficult to define the meaning of a phraseological unit as it is connected with many lingual and extra lingual aspects – logical and psychological, historical and philosophical. Lexis and syntax, or vocabulary (phraseology as a part of vocabulary) and grammar, have traditionally been viewed as discrete aspects of language in teaching (Hoey, 2005; Romer, 2009), but a growing number of scholars from a variety of theoretical camps within applied linguistics and second language acquisition argue that the two are in fact inseparable (e.g. cognitive linguists, constructionists, and corpus linguists). The importance of phraseological studies is permanently discussed as it demonstrates the interrelation between the language and the society. The article is centered on the problem of meaning of word-components in a phraseological unit. Considering all possible points of view, the authors keep to the four types of word-components in phraseological units: real words– word-components with ad verbum meaning; potential words– word-components with weak meaning; “former” words – word-components with re-comprehended meaning; “ghost-words”- with word-components that do not exist in the language.

Main body

As you know, word combinations which are turned into phraseological units are included in complex semantic processes. Phraseologists have not yet reached a common opinion on a mechanism and regularities of changing a semantic essence of words-components of phraseological units. A formal semantic structure of the phraseological unit, i.e. the study of its plane of content and plane of expression, represents a special issue. In other words, the question is how elements of semantics of phraseological units are classified by their lexical components, i.e. a degree of a so-called semantic combination and semantic dividedness of the phraseological unit [1]. Phraseological units are stable expressions that cannot be translated literally, since they have their own

¹ *Iskandarova Nilufar Tokhirovna, English teacher at Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages*

meaning, which differs from the meanings of individual words in the expression. This is an integral part of the English language, they are found in dialogues, letters, books, etc. Phraseologisms can be formed in different ways. Some of them have historical roots or are associated with specific cultural and social contexts. For example, the expression to break the ice (to break through the ice) arose in those days when ships used an ice ax to break through the ice cover. Even centuries later, this expression is used in everyday speech.

Other phraseological units arise with the help of metaphors and symbols. Consider the expression to be over the moon (to be in seventh heaven). It expresses happiness, and its origin is associated with the idea that somewhere at the very top of the universe is the seventh heaven, the sacred territory of the gods and angels. Some phraseological units are nothing more than a play on words. For example, to have a frog in one's throat (speak with a scratchy throat). This expression means that a person has health problems. But its origin is due to the fact that the voice, when tickled, resembles the croaking of a frog [2]. Phraseological synonyms also play an important role in the field of phraseology. Phraseologisms can be used to express any idea, but with the help of phraseological synonyms they can be used in different contexts in different stylistic ways. The components of phraseology are often figurative. Phraseologisms, which are composed of components that have a figurative meaning has their original meaning hidden behind them. There are also synonyms that have the same meaning in different languages and can be equivalent to each other. "The exact equivalent is a phraseology that has the same meaning in different languages," said Borisova in her scientific views. Such phrases can be found in different languages. However, the translations of their meanings do not always match. Also, if we want to translate them as expressions, expressions such as from head to toe from thread to needle from hair to tail are synonymous phraseological units that are equally suitable for translating these phraseologies. The family is an important society of intra family relations between people. The group of phraseological units reflecting family or kinship relations includes units that reveal the national and cultural characteristics of marriage, family, clan and family relations [Terpak, 2006, p. 9]. The group of phraseological units reflecting family or kinship relations includes units that reveal the national and cultural characteristics of marriage, family, clan and kinship [3].

In the Uzbek linguistic culture, the male stereotype consists of the following concepts: education, work, marriage, family, the role of breadwinner, responsibility, caring for parents, career advancement, ensuring the future for children, caring for grandchildren. As can be seen from the components of the male gender stereotype, masculinity, career growth, the role of breadwinner, and family are identical in both languages. However, in the Uzbek linguistic culture, the stereotype of a man requires more responsibility and care, and not only about his family, but also about his elderly parents and even grandchildren. Such a chain of mutual concern in Uzbek culture strengthens family ties and removes a man from unnecessary entertainment. The concept of "kinship relations" is reflected in linguistic units with kinship terms that convey information about the types of kinship [4]. The study of phraseological units with the terms of kinship made it possible to divide kinship into two main groups:

1. Blood relations and close family relations;
2. Distant kinship relations, including clan ties.

This classification of family relationships was first proposed by Yu.I. Levin, who distinguished blood and non-blood relationship. From multi-system languages in this paragraph to the analysis English and Uzbek phraseological units related to the concept sphere “family” are involved. The diversity of these languages makes it possible to conduct a typological study of the reflection of the concept of “family” in English and Uzbek phraseological units and to identify the national specifics of family traditions and relationships.

Phraseological unities are much more numerous. They are partially motivated word-groups because their meaning can be usually guessed from the meaning of its components through the metaphorical meaning of the whole phraseological unit. The classification of phraseological units on a semantic principle was suggested by the prominent Russian scholar V.V.Vinogradov, who made the great contribution to this branch of linguistic science. He took into account the degree of idiomaticity (motivation of meaning) of phraseological units that is the relationship existing between the meaning of the whole and the meaning of their component parts. In other words, he considered the degree of semantic cohesion between the components of phraseological units: the more distant the meaning of a phraseological unit from the current meaning of its constituent parts, the greater is its degree of semantic cohesion. Thus, according to this principal Academician Vinogradov V.V. pointed out three types of phraseological units, namely phraseological fusions, phraseological unities and phraseological collocations. Phraseological fusions are completely non-motivated word groups. The meaning of the whole in phraseological fusions cannot be deduced at least synchronically from the meanings of its constituent parts [5]. So, the degree of motivation is very low in this case, and idiomaticity is, as a rule, combined with complete stability of the lexical components and the grammatical structure of the fusion. Phraseological fusions are specific for every language and do not lend themselves to literal translation into other languages.

Usage of phraseological units. English phraseological units must be memorized only as integral expressions, always check the meanings in the dictionary, pay attention to examples of use, avoiding translating them into words. So, the expression to let the cat out of the bag has nothing to do with cats (cat) and bags (bag), but was formed at one time due to the fact that sellers at fairs used bags with cats instead of real goods to deceive buyers. If you use this expression, you must remember that it means to give away a secret or expose someone’s plans, not to free a furry pet. In addition, phraseological units can have different levels of formality. Most of them are more suitable for colloquial speech. For example, in the meaning of starting something, the expression to get the ball rolling is more informal than to commence proceedings. Therefore, it is important to keep track of what is appropriate to use in a friendly conversation, and which expressions are best avoided in business documents. Phraseologisms can have different degrees of use depending on the region and culture. To take a rain check (reschedule to another day) is a very popular phrase in the US, but may not be familiar to native English speakers from other countries.

Conclusion

To sum up, all possible points of view are discussed and four types of words in phraseological units are defined: real words, potential words, “former” words, ghost-words. The process of phraseological units forming is complicated and continuous theoretically and practically that is connected with the development of civilization and teaching phraseology should consider both linguistic and extra

linguistic aspects. Successful foreign language teaching presupposes knowing both the methodology of teaching and the theory of the language. Teaching phraseology is a part of cultural approach to foreign teaching and organizing vocabulary, phraseology according to structure of components is a linguistic approach in English teaching vocabulary. Therefore, in order to avoid misunderstandings when using phraseological units, it is important not only to know their meaning, but also to take into account the context, the level of formality and the dialect of the interlocutor with whom you are communicating.

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